

Fluid Dispenser Prototype: A Time Based Approach

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Abstract—In today's era when precise, accurate and time efficient systems are in great demand, automated techniques supersede manual practices. As a need of time, we introduce a wireless, automated, cost effective, yet reliable and efficient system of fluid dispensing. Our prototype system can dispense varying amounts of fluids in milliliters (maximum 1L) as per demand of the user. It uses the principle of time based fluid dispensing achieved through the built-in timer property of the AT89C51 microcontroller. To satisfy the principle used and verify the system's accuracy, fluids of varying viscosities were dispensed and monitored. The experimental results of the wireless fluid dispensing system when tested showed linear relationship between the dispensing time and desired volumes of fluids having differing viscosities. The added feature of wireless control using HM-TRP series transceiver module along with on-site control via a keypad eliminated the need of physical presence of operator within the range of 10 meters in order to make the system operational. This system can be used in pharmaceutical and beverage industries as well as in different laboratories for dispensing and filling volumes of fluids with varying viscosities.

Index Terms—Fluid dispensing system, microcontroller, pharmaceutical industry, time-based dispensing, and wireless.

I. INTRODUCTION

The high throughput and safety demands of today have resulted in an increased need for automotive approaches to substitute earlier manual techniques [1]. We have state of the art machines nearly in every field to enhance production efficiency, accuracy and satisfaction. Our clinical laboratories, pharmaceutical industries, environmental, chemical, food and beverage companies are no exception to this. In all the mentioned industries sample preparation process is of critical importance especially with respect to pharmaceutical and food industry. The quality of the end products strongly relies on the correct and accurate dispensing of needed volumes for the ingredients being mixed each time [2]. For instance, in food and beverage companies mixing of exact volumes of syrup with carbonated fluid is important to acquire the proper taste. The demands of pharmaceutical companies are more severe as incorrect concentrations of drugs or injections can lead to life threatening results [3]. To attain this level of perfection, use of automation techniques for fluid measurement and dispensing is a necessity in place of manual methods which are prone to errors.

A literature survey provided us with a spectrum of automated techniques used for fluid dispensing along with several designs of dispensing systems proposed by various

inventors. Hickerson [4], Ceccarelli et al. [5] and Awada et al. [6] patented different devices but they all lacked the features of a pump and the ability for the user to control the quantity of liquid being dispensed. An improved liquid measuring and dispensing device was then proposed by Hanson in connection to cooking oil measurement and dispensing overcoming the deficiencies of the devices developed by aforementioned inventors [7]. A general purpose precise volume fluid dispenser was invented by Takacs to be used in pharmaceutical, beverage, concrete mixing and other industries. It consisted of pressure level sensor, bubbler tube, and a controller that controls the inflow and outflow of the precise volume of liquids from the entire system [8]. Butler et al. described a chemical storage and injection system for automatic dispensing of desired volumes of chemicals for industrial applications. His method included the utilization of sensors, valves and a controller for controlling the dual chamber filling and metered dispensing of the chemicals into a vessel [2].

Few well known and widely used fluid dispensing techniques are time-pressure dispensing and volumetric fluid dispensing using either pinch valves or positive displacement piston pumps [9]. Time pressure dispensing involves application of air pressure to the top of a container holding the fluid, forcing the material to be dispensed from its outlet. The amount of fluid to be dispensed is directly linked to the length of time the pressure is applied along with other factors. These systems are widely used but are difficult to control [10]. The second technique is volumetric fluid dispensing using pinch valves. This includes a tube or cylinder whose volume is already known, employed between a fluid reservoir and a filling vessel. When this tube or cylinder is filled with the desired volume often determined by optical sensors, the premeasured fluid is allowed to be dispensed using pinch valves [9]. The volumetric positive displacement piston pump utilizes a tube of desired volume enclosed by pistons from either ends. The sequence of downward and upward stroke of the piston governs the filling and dispensing of the predetermined amount of fluid. This method has been found advantageous due to its precise dispensing capability irrespective of the material's viscosity [11].

Our work presented here is about the design and implementation of a cost effective, reliable and flexible prototype of a wireless automated adjustable fluid dispensing system. Time based dispensing technique was employed and the designed system can be used in clinical labs and pharmaceutical industry. The salient feature of our proposed system is the wireless controlling of the entire process of dispensing a precise and user defined quantity of fluid into vessels from a distance range of 10 meters.

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II. METHODOLOGY

The low cost fluid dispensing system was developed using microcontroller “Atmel AT89C51” [12]. The flow of the system was programmed in assembly language. The principle utilized for dispensing precise, accurate and user defined volumes of fluids was ‘time based dispensing’ i.e. the amount of fluid to be dispensed will be determined by the time taken by that fluid to dispense completely [10]. To provide automation to the system, the timer facility of the micro controller was used. By a series of experiments, an average time was determined to dispense a fluid having a volume of 1ml. This time was loaded in the micro controller's timer through programming to control the opening and closing of solenoid valve along with the working of the pump. We aimed to investigate the working accuracy of the fluid dispenser by dispensing three different fluids having increased viscosities in the order of less viscous, slightly viscous and highly viscous fluids. A separate time factor was measured for each type of fluid to be used in programming. We also tested the optimum working range of our developed wireless prototype using the HM-TRP module [13].

A. System Components

The system hardware involved in the development of the wireless fluid dispensing system is shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Components involved in the development of wireless operated fluid dispensing system

TABLE I
AT89C51 PORTS AND THEIR FUNCTION/CONTROL IN WIRELESS FLUID DISPENSING SYSTEM

Ports of AT89C51	Function/Control
P0.0 – P0.3	Keypad
P1	LCD
P2.1	Pump
P2.2	Solenoid valve
P2.3	IR trigger input
P2.4	Conveyer belt motor
P3.0	Serial output (HM-TRP Transmitter)
P3.1	Serial input (HM-TRP receiver)

1) HM-TRP Module

In this work, HM-TRP module developed by Hope Microelectronic Co. Ltd was chosen for remote selection of fluid volume and initialization of the dispensing system. HM-TRP module was used to reduce the number of wires connected, introducing portability and reducing the cost comparative to wired Ethernet network connectivity. This wireless module was preferred as it is a low cost, high performance transparent frequency shifting key (FSK) transceiver with a range of operating frequencies of 433, 470, 868 and 915 MHz [13]. The HM-TRP module consisted of two main divisions. The first one was used to transmit the user's remote control input and the other one was utilized to receive the data from the remote control through AT89C51 microcontroller pin 3.1 (See Table 1). The HM-TRP module is illustrated in Figure 2.

2) Microcontroller (Atmel 89c51)

In this study, AT89C51 microcontroller was used to control the dispensing of the various fluids either from HM-TRP module or keypad input. Microcontroller AT89C51 was selected due to its useful features of having low power consumption, 4K bytes of flash memory and low unit cost specifications [12]. It is also widely used in the development of medical instruments and systems. Table I lists various ports of AT89C51 utilized in controlling the fluid dispensing process. The schematic diagram for the connection between the AT89C51 and HM-TRP DB9 connector is represented in Figure 3 (a).

3) Keypad

In our fluid dispensing system the keypad was an alternative to the wireless HM-TRP module and was embedded at the site and frame of the fluid dispensing system. We used a 16 button hex membrane keypad arranged in a 4*4 matrix [14] with its appropriate encoder IC [15]. The keypad was interfaced to port 0 of the microcontroller for giving inputs and schematic diagram is illustrated in Figure 3 (b).

Fig. 2. Representation of HM-TRP module [13]

Fig. 3. Schematic representations of the developed fluid dispensing system: a) AT89C51 connections with the HM-TRP module DB9 connector; (b) AT89C51 interfaced with the keypad; (c) AT89C51 linkage with the IR trigger; (d) AT89C51 port connections with the solenoid valve, pump and conveyor motor circuit

The keypad consisted of ten numeric buttons labeled 0 to 9 incorporated for volume selection and six alphabetic keys A to F. Only two alphabetic buttons A and B were used for calibration and starting of the system respectively. The work of the keypad encoder was to ensure 4 bit binary output in order to reduce interfacing pins with the controller [12, 14].

4) IR Trigger

An Infra Red (IR) light emitting diode (transmitter) and a light dependent resistor (receiver) was used as a trigger circuit to detect the presence of a graduated vessel for starting the fluid dispensing cycle. In case of no obstacle in between the IR LED and LDR which were distanced apart at 10 cm; a high logic output was generated. But as soon as a vessel arrived for filling and disturbed the light intensity, its output went low. This change of logic was detected by the microcontroller at port 2.3 and as a result it stopped the conveyor belt motor. The IR trigger connection with the AT89C51 is shown in Figure 3 (c).

5) Conveyor System

Rubber material was used for the construction of conveyor belt system. The two ends of the belt were mounted on pulleys; one was powered while the other was idler. This system was steered by a 12 V and 300 mA dc gear motor which in turn drove the pulley. A single pole double throw (SPDT) relay [16] and a LM 324 amplifier [17] constituted its driving circuitry. The motor's on off status was controlled by port 2.1 of the controller.

6) Pump

A 12 V dc aquarium pump was used to draw the fluid contained in the rectangular reservoir to the graduated containers that are to be filled. The working of the pump was controlled by the controller from port 2.1 through a driving circuit containing a SPDT relay and a LM 324 amplifier. Upon pressing the calibration button, the pump is switched on for 2 ms which removes all air bubbles from the tubing.

7) Solenoid valve

At the end of the reservoir tubing a 12 V dc solenoid valve [18] was housed to control the flow of liquid to be dispensed. It was controlled by controller port 2.2 via a driving circuit made of SPDT relay and a LM 324 amplifiers. After dispensing the programmed fluid volume, the valve closes automatically. Upon pressing the calibration button, the controller opens the solenoid valve, hence opening the flow tube. The connection of AT89C51 with the solenoid valve, pump and conveyor system is represented in Figure 3 (d).

8) Liquid Crystal Display (LCD)

A liquid crystal display (LCD) of 20 x 2 (20 characters, 2 lines) was used [19] to show the user the format in which the system expects the inputs as well as to indicate the received fluid volume in milliliters (ml). It was interfaced with the controller at port 1. The maximum fluid volume that can be displayed and dispensed using this system is 1000 ml (1L).

B. System Flow Chart

Figure 4 shows the flowchart illustrating the working of our programmable time based fluid dispensing system. The cycle starts by sending a signal to the conveyer belt motor either through the keypad or the remote control, following which it starts moving. The graduated vessels to be filled by dispensing controlled volume of fluids are placed on this belt. The controller waits for an input signal from the IR sensor, which is received as the sensor detects a vessel in front of it and beneath the dispensing system. Instantly, a control signal is sent to halt the conveyer's motor.

Fig. 4. Flow chart representing the software description of the fluid dispensing system.

The actual dispensing process commences after a user defined volume is input in milliliters either via the keypad or the HM-TRP wireless set. The controller generate control signals to open the solenoid valve and to start the pump respectively which were initially close. As the dispensing solenoid valve opens allowing the fluid to be released into the vessels, a built in timer also starts. The dispensing continues till the timer expires. The controller then sends out control signals to stop the pump and close the solenoid valve respectively, completing the dispense cycle. The conveyer belt proceeds to bring the next vessel in line to be filled and the procedure is repeated until all the containers are filled with the desired amount of fluid.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The testing was performed on the developed equipment to determine the relationship between the volume of fluid and the time taken by it to dispense the required volume into a graduated flask. For this purpose, the experimentations were carried out iteratively on less viscous, slightly viscous, and highly viscous fluids for the user defined volume fillings in a series of marked vessels. Ten different volumes of each kind of fluid were taken with a 100 ml gap between each volume sample. We observed a linear relationship between the volume of the fluids and the time taken to dispense those fluids as represented in Figure 5. The same figure also describes that increased time was required to fill highly viscous fluid for a given volume as compared to slightly viscous and less viscous fluids. For instance, the time taken to fill the 400 ml volume of more viscous fluid was 33.4 sec in contrast to 20 sec for slight viscous and 10 sec for less viscous fluids. This shows that there occurs a direct relationship between time taken to dispense a fluid and its viscosity keeping the volume as a constant variable. The more viscous a fluid is, the more time it takes to flow and to be dispensed.

The system was also checked for its wireless operability from a varying distance of up to 15 meters using the HM-TRP module. It demonstrated satisfied and accurate working of the wireless prototype dispensing system from a distance of 10 meters while beyond this range the signals were not reached at the receiving end.

A wireless and adjustable fluid dispensing setup provided with a lot of flexibility to the user in terms of volume selection and mobility. At the same time, the time based dispensing method reduced the hardware and cost of the dispensing system which would otherwise increase if volumetric positive displacement piston pump or time-pressure dispensing techniques were employed.

Fig. 5. Plot representing the relationship between the volume of the fluid (ml) and the time (sec) required to dispense the fluid. Blue line plot defines less viscous fluid, red line plot represents the slightly viscous fluid and the green line plot illustrates highly viscous fluid respectively.

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

A wireless adjustable fluid dispensing system was successfully developed in connection to a prospective usage in the pharmaceutical, food and beverage companies and clinical labs for time based dispensing of different fluids with varying viscosities. It allowed its operator to wirelessly control the working of the system from a distance other than the feature of on-site operation. Future modifications include wireless and distant control of such systems by distance enhancement beyond 15 meters and dispensing lesser fluid volumes ranging below 1 ml. Remote distance monitoring and control features can be achieved through the use of programmable logic controllers; and their enhancement by supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) for potential studies. The decrease in pump size and tubing system will allow micro liter fluid dispensing desired for micro level applications. Prospective studies will also emphasize on enhancing system accuracy. Fluid flow sensing technique through the use of fluid flow meter can be used rather than time based technique and concentration measurement circuit can be incorporated for concentration based fillings.

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REFERENCES

- [1] J. X. Liu, *New developments in robotics research*: Nova Publishers, 2005.
- [2] J. Butler, T. Elsayy, R. M. Hall, W. Atkins, and E. Hansen, "Chemical Dispensing system and method," ed: Google Patents, 2001.
- [3] A. Godschalk Jr Louis, "Device for dispensing measured quantities of liquid," ed: Google Patents, 1968.
- [4] F. R. Hickerson, "Liquid dispensing system." U.S. Patent No. 5,044,527. 3 Sep. 1991.
- [5] L. R. Ceccarelli, and A. Ceccarelli. "Pre-measured liquid and powder dispenser with overflow lube." U.S. Patent No. 5,323,938. 28 Jun. 1994.
- [6] H. Awada, and K. Awada. "Reusable and accurately pre-measured liquid dispenser." U.S. Patent No. 5,584,420. 17 Dec. 1996.
- [7] T. R. Hanson, "Liquid measuring and dispensing device," ed: Google Patents, 2005.
- [8] G. W. Takacs, "Precise volume fluid dispenser," ed: Google Patents, 1996.
- [9] J. R. Randall Jr and D. E. Keyes, "Time Volumetric Fluid Dispensing Apparatus," ed: Google Patents, 2011.
- [10] D. Dixon, "Time pressure dispensing," White papers. Universal Instruments. http://www4.uic.com/wcms/WCMS2.nsf/index/Resources_58.html. Accessed, vol. 11, 2009.
- [11] P. Swanson, "Improving industrial dispensing with pneumatic dispensing valves," Intertronics, 2007.
- [12] AT89C51, "bit Microcontroller data sheet," Atmel Corporation, 2000.
- [13] HM-TRP module, "HM-TRP-RS485 Series 100mW Transceiver modules V1.0," Hope Microelectronics Co., Ltd, 2014.
- [14] Parallax, "4x4 Matrix Membrane Keypad" Parallax Inc., 2011.
- [15] E-Lab Digital Engineering "EDE1144 Keypad Encoder IC: 4 x 4 Matrix Keypad Encoder IC", E-Lab Digital Engineering, Inc, 1999.
- [16] M. Nakao, A. Sasabata, and H. Tanaka, "SPST switch, SPDT switch, and communication apparatus using the SPDT switch," ed: Google Patents, 2001.
- [17] T. Instruments, "LM124-N/LM224-N/LM324-N/LM2902-N Low Power Quad Operational Amplifiers," Texas Instruments, 2004.
- [18] Solenoid valve, "General pupose Solenoid valves," Parker Fluid Control Division (FCD), 2011.
- [19] J. Ilett, "How to use intelligent LCDs," *Everyday Practical Electronics*, pp. 84-89, 1997.